

target CRM	Al	Mg	Ti	Mg	Ti	Mn	Ni	Cu	P	PGMs	Al	Cu	Mg		
application/waste flow	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P9 O1 I7) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Al dross (P0 O3 O4*, P0 O3 O8*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.	Al dross (P0 O3 O8*) - this waste flow results from secondary Al smelting and fluxing.	Al dross (P0 O3 O4*, P0 O3 O8*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.		
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill		
(Partially) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Recovery of Al via physical separation processes	Recovery of Mg as alloying element in recovered Al	Recovery of Ti as alloying element in recovered Al	Recovery of Mg as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Ti as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Mn as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Ni as alloying element in recovered stainless steel	Recovery of Cu via physical separation processes	N.A.	By-product (downstream) from recovered Cu via physical separation processes	Hydro- and pyrometallurgical treatment	N.A.	N.A.		
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?													
3.5	Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Physical separation separates Al from non-Al fraction. The output is a mixture of Al alloys. (Bunge, 2016) Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Magnetic steel can be separated with magnetic separation. Different steel grades can be detected with handheld XRF devices or sensor-based sorting technologies.	Magnetic steel can be separated with magnetic separation. Different steel grades can be detected with handheld XRF devices or sensor-based sorting technologies.	Magnetic steel can be separated with magnetic separation. Different steel grades can be detected with handheld XRF devices or sensor-based sorting technologies.	Magnetic steel (only ferritic and martensitic, not austenitic) can be separated with magnetic separation. Different steel grades can be detected with handheld XRF devices or sensor-based sorting technologies.	Physical separation separates Cu from non-Cu fraction. The output is a mixture of Cu alloys. (Bunge, 2016) Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction.	No available purification techniques	PGMs are mostly alloyed in Cu. Physical separation separates Cu from non-Cu fraction. The output is a mixture of Cu alloys. (Bunge, 2016)	Partially	No technology available, even at low TRL	No technology available, even at low TRL	
3.6	Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	It is usually not intended to recover the alloying elements by extraction and refining, but to functionally recover alloying elements in different steel grades after pre-sorting via remelting. The composition is adjusted by adding the required alloying elements. The better the pre-sorting, the lower the requirements for composition adjustments.	It is usually not intended to recover the alloying elements by extraction and refining, but to functionally recover alloying elements in different steel grades after pre-sorting via remelting. The composition is adjusted by adding the required alloying elements. The better the pre-sorting, the lower the requirements for composition adjustments.	It is usually not intended to recover the alloying elements by extraction and refining, but to functionally recover alloying elements in different steel grades after pre-sorting via remelting. The composition is adjusted by adding the required alloying elements. The better the pre-sorting, the lower the requirements for composition adjustments.	It is usually not intended to recover the alloying elements by extraction and refining, but to functionally recover alloying elements in different steel grades after pre-sorting via remelting. The composition is adjusted by adding the required alloying elements. The better the pre-sorting, the lower the requirements for composition adjustments.	Pyro- and hydrometallurgy yield high quality product - pure Cu scrap can be remelted, more complex waste flows can be used as an input material in an integrated Cu smelter	No available purification techniques	Hydrometallurgical by-product from Cu purification can be refined into high purity PGMs	Yes, high TRL	No technology available, even at low TRL	No technology available, even at low TRL
economic criteria															
4.1	Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated copper smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated copper smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated copper smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is a steel scrap market.	There is a Cu scrap market.	Not pure and contaminated with heavy metals. Not suitable as fertilizer	Market available, already established	There is a market, but the quality is generally lower than primary Al from bauxite.	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible			
4.2	Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM?	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	No	No	No	No	Cheaper from secondary resources due to higher concentration in input material	No	Cheaper from secondary resources due to higher concentration of input material	Unknown, generally cheaper than primary but lower quality.	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible
4.3	Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024)	Landfill taxes (EEA, 2024); recovery is associated with copper recovery	Landfill taxes	Landfill taxes	Landfill taxes
4.4	Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?	Many operational plants (TRL-9) (FIR, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Plant in Magdeburg, Germany from MDSU and Steinert using eddy current technology followed by XRT and XRF (Schmidt, 2025)	Many operational plants (TRL-9) (FIR, 2025)	No	Many operational plants (TRL-9) (FIR, 2025)	Yes, high TRL	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible
4.5	Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?	Recovery of Al scrap enables the recovery of other resources	No	No	No	No	No	No	Recovery of Cu scrap enables the recovery of other resources	No	Enabled by Cu recovery	No	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Not relevant as this is technologically not feasible
environmental criteria															
5.1	Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?	Extensive trade schemes of bottom ash already established	No	No	No	No	No	No	Extensive trade schemes of bottom ash already established	No	Extensive trade schemes of bottom ash already established	Yes	Unknown, not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Unknown, not relevant as this is technologically not feasible
5.2	Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?	No chemical requirements, only moderate energy requirements for physical separation	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not available	No chemical requirements, only moderate energy requirements for physical separation	Not available	No chemical requirements, only moderate energy requirements for physical separation	Not available	Not available	Not available
5.3	Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?	Low chemical and energy requirements in general for secondary Al smelting compared to primary.	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high	Similar energy and chemical requirements for refining compared to primary production. No ore beneficiation required.	Unknown	Similar energy and chemical requirements for refining compared to primary production. No ore beneficiation required.	Lower energy and chemical requirements for refining compared to primary production.	Unknown, not relevant as this is technologically not feasible	Unknown, not relevant as this is technologically not feasible
5.4	Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?	Physical treatment of bottom ash reduces environmental impact. Smelting of Al scrap produces black dross, which is hazardous. Treatment of the latter is established and obligated by EU regulation.	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	No more than primary	Contaminated by heavy metals	No more than primary	Treatment is done to mitigate environmental impact, recovery is a by-product of this treatment.	Treatment is done to mitigate environmental impact, recovery is a by-product of this treatment.	Treatment is done to mitigate environmental impact, recovery is a by-product of this treatment.
5.5	Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?	Very low compared to primary Al, but primary and secondary Al are very different materials.	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Armatulu & Armatulu, 2018; EuRic, n.d.)	Heavy metal and salt contamination	Comparable to primary PGMs, but no impact from mining	Treatment of dross is encouraged by the Waste Framework Directive	Treatment of dross is encouraged by the Waste Framework Directive	Treatment of dross is encouraged by the Waste Framework Directive

target CRM		Al	Mg	Ti	Mg	Ti	Mn	Ni	Cu	P	PGMs	Al	Cu	Mg
application/waste flow		Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (P 01 P1*) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of household waste and cannot be considered as a product anymore. It is heterogeneous mixture of very fine to coarse particles consisting of metals, glass, ceramic, organic material...	Al dross (P 03 O4*, P 03 O8*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.	Al dross (P 03 O8*) - this waste flow results from secondary Al smelting and fluxing.	Al dross (P 03 O4*, P 03 O8*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery		Landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill									
(Partially) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery		Recovery of Al via physical separation processes	Recovery of Mg as alloying element in recovered Al	Recovery of Ti as alloying element in recovered Al	Recovery of Mg as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Ti as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Mn as alloying element in recovered steel	Recovery of Ni as alloying element in recovered stainless steel	Recovery of Cu via physical separation processes	N.A.	By-product (downstream) from recovered Cu via physical separation processes	Hydro- and pyrometallurgical treatment	N.A.	N.A.
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?												
legal criteria														
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?	No	No	No	No								
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?	No	No	No	No								
6.3	Legal Incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?	Waste Framework Directive and Landfill Directive	Waste Framework Directive and Landfill Directive	No	No								
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?	Metal Scrap Regulation	Copper Scrap Regulation	No	No	No	No	No					

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Abbreviations used

BOF	Basic Oxygen Furnace
CRM	Critical Raw Material
EAF	Electric Arc Furnace
EU	European Union
LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
PGM	Platinum Group Metal
REE	Rare Earth Elements
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
XRT	X-ray transmission

Implementing Regulation EU 2025/973	Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/973 of 23 May 2025 amending and correcting Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 authorising certain products and substances for use in organic production and establishing their lists
Copper Scrap Regulation (EU) No 715/2013	Commission Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 of 25 July 2013 establishing criteria determining when Cu scrap ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council
Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC	Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste
Metal Scrap Regulation (EU) No 333/2011	Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 of 31 March 2011 establishing criteria determining when certain types of scrap metal cease to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council
Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC	Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives